

Energy $\rightarrow \hbar/\Delta(t)$ and Momentum $\rightarrow \hbar/\Delta(x)$ from $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4$?

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We consider the special relativistic relation $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4$ ($\hbar=1, c=1$) and write it as: $E = \sqrt{p^2 + m_0^2}$. As $m_0 \rightarrow 0$ and $v \rightarrow c$ at the same time (i.e. the photon case), one has: $E = pc$, but at the same time, $\Delta x = c \Delta t$ in any frame. This suggests that Δx and Δt are not fixed constants, but change with frame and that E is proportional to $1/\Delta(t)$ and p to $1/\Delta(x)$ in the $m_0 \rightarrow 0, v \rightarrow c$ limit.

In the $m_0 > 0, v \ll c$ case, $\Delta(x) = v \Delta(t) + \text{mocc} \sqrt{1-vv/cc} / \text{constant}$ which does not coincide with $\Delta_1(x) = v \Delta_1(t)$. This begs the question: Why have two sets of measures for x and t ? We note that in the photon case, even though there is one set, it is linked with two experimental results. The first is the measurement of speed and the second is two-slit interference. Thus, in the $m_0 > 0$ case, one may have two sets, one to measure speed and the other interference and there is no reason for these to coincide. Thus, we argue that special relativity actually suggests an intrinsic $\Delta(x)$ and $\Delta(t)$ proportional to $1/p$ and $1/E$, which do not transform as a 4-vector.

$E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4$

$E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4$ ((1)) is a basic result of special relativity which holds for both photons ($m_0=0, v=c$) and particles with rest mass ($m_0>0, v<c$). In particular,

$$E = \text{mocc} / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \text{ and } p = \text{mov} / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((2))$$

Then:

$$E = \text{ccpv} + \text{mo} \text{cccc} \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((3))$$

In the photon case, $\sqrt{1-vv/cc} = 0$, so ((3)) becomes:

$$E = pc \quad ((4a)), \text{ but at the same time: } \Delta(x) = c \Delta(t) \quad ((4b))$$

Furthermore, c is the same in any frame, but E and p change. ((4a)) and ((4b)) imply that:

$$E = \text{constant} / \Delta(t) \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p = \text{constant} / \Delta(x) \quad ((5b))$$

The point is that $\Delta(x)$ and $\Delta(t)$ do not transform as (x, ct) , a 4-vector, as one would expect. In other words, in the photon case, given an energy E and a momentum p , special relativity implies that there exist intrinsic $\Delta(x)$ and $\Delta(t)$ values proportional to $1/p$ and $1/E$.

The Case of $m_0 > 0$

For a rest mass, $m_0 > 0$, one may still have $v \rightarrow c$, which yields the same result. Thus, in the high $v \rightarrow c$ case, the arguments for a photon apply to ((3)) and one again has: ((5a)) and ((5b)).

There does not seem to be much point considering the limit $m_0 \rightarrow 0$.

If $E = \text{constant}/\Delta(t)$ and $p = \text{constant}/\Delta(x)$ for all $m_0 > 0$ and $v < c$ values, then:

$$\Delta(x) = \Delta(t) v + m_0 c^2 \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} / \text{constant} \quad ((6))$$

For a particle with rest mass in the $v \ll c$ limit, intrinsic $\Delta(x)$ and $\Delta(t)$ intervals exist based on $1/E$ and $1/p$ and these do not transform as a 4-vector. Furthermore, one has two independent equations, ((6)) and:

$$\Delta_1(x) = \Delta_1(t) v \quad ((7))$$

The $\Delta(x)$ and $\Delta(t)$ in ((6)) do not define $\Delta_1(x)$ and $\Delta_1(t)$ except in the photon case. It is not surprising that the photon case has a special property given that $\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ appears in special relativity, singling it out. The question then becomes: How does one distinguish between $\Delta(x)$, $\Delta(t)$ of ((6)) and $\Delta_1(x)$, $\Delta_1(t)$ of ((7))?

If one considers the case of a photon, it is known that it moves like a particle according to $x = ct + x_0$, but also has a wavelength and frequency, the former which may be measured in a 2-slit experiment. A wavelength may be associated with a $\Delta(x)$, and motion with $\Delta_1(x)$ with similar results for $\Delta(t)$ and $\Delta_1(t)$. Thus, there are experimental ways of measuring both $\Delta_1(x)$, $\Delta_1(t)$ and $\Delta(x)$, $\Delta(t)$, the latter being linked with 2-slit experiments. This suggests that $\Delta(x)$ for $m_0 > 0$ may also be measured using a 2-slit experiment for a particle with rest mass, as has been done long ago.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that the notion of $E = \text{constant} / \Delta(t)$ and $p = \text{constant} / \Delta(x)$ may follow from $EE = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$. We rewrite this as: $E = pv + m_0 c^2 \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and note that in the photon case: $E = pc$ which together with $\Delta(x) = c \Delta(t)$ gives the relation. The problem is that for $m_0 > 0$, $v \ll c$: $\Delta(x) = v \Delta(t) + m_0 c^2 \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} / \text{constant}$ and at the same time: $\Delta_1(x) = v \Delta_1(t)$. Thus, $\Delta(x)$, $\Delta(t)$ cannot be the same as $\Delta_1(x)$, $\Delta_1(t)$, but are the same in the photon case. This begs the question: Why have two sets? In the photon case, $\Delta_1(x)$ and $\Delta_1(t)$ measure linear motion, while $\Delta(x)$ is associated with 2-slit interference. These two happen to coincide for the photon. Thus, one may suggest that $\Delta(x)$ for $m_0 > 0$ should be linked with 2-slit interference, and hence has physical meaning. We note that these results imply an intrinsic $\Delta(x)$ and $\Delta(t)$ associated with $1/p$ and $1/E$ and so transform differently from (x, ct) , a 4-vector.